

SECOND AWAKENING OF THE ELECTRIC CAR INDUSTRY

Shavqiyev Elbek

Student Of The Faculty of Transport of Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

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Abstract: This article analyzes the creation of electric vehicles, the emergence of the second renaissance at the beginning of the 21st century and its main causes, as well as the changes that have occurred in the electric vehicle industry in recent years.

Keywords: car, electric car, hybrid cars, automotive industry. batteries battery, Tesla, BYD, Detroit Electric.

Electric car-means to an independent source of electricity (battery of accumulators, solar panels, wind generators, condensates, and flammable elements), using one or more electrodvigatels a moving car is understood. Early electric cars had internal combustion engines and internal combustion engines appeared before the car. Hungarian inventor Anjos Jedlik in 1828 an electric stroller similar to a skateboard more often than a car demonstrated. Re-used as an electrical energy source in cars by the French physicist Gaston Plante on rechargeable accumulators a somewhat successful step was taken, which was rechargeable in 1859 the first battery of solid-state batteries was invented, but the charge of the battery of these batteries is 10 m³ ni, one since the time of charging times is 500 hours.

Volkmar electrodes tried the use of additional grilles as and became the first rechargeable, powdery compact solid acid batteries cashed his battery. This is one of the first major steps in the field of electric cars one.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

By French scientist Gustave Trouvé in November 1881 in Paris the electric car was presented to the public at the last international electrical exhibition. These three are the electric car with wheels was able to reach speeds of up to 12 km / h and with a full charge it covered about 26 km. In 1894, American inventors Morris and hello to a simple car created a similar electric car. 4 in this electric car, which received the name " Elektrobat " there are 2 with 1.5 HP, as there are places for the wheel, two Wayfarer. the engine allowed the car to accelerate to 32 km / h. Of the electric car. the total mass was 750 kg. Racing driver Camille Genazzi "La Jamais Contente " in April 1899 land-based 100 kilometer speed through a special electric car exceeded the limit, the official speed is 105,882 km/h.

The record for the longest distance in a full charge is "Borland Electric" was installed in an electric car, which covered 167 km from Chicago to Milwaukee. The next day (after fully charged) the electric car with its own power returned to Chicago, the average speed was 55 mph. One of the fans of improving electric cars at the beginning of the 20th century the famous American inventor was Thomas Edison. It was monetized as "Detroit Electric" the electric car is powered by a 160 km road at a power output of. It took a lot of effort to create a battery and did it. In 1914, Edison, together with Ford, launched a mass of inexpensive electric cars planned to start production. But burned out at Edison's lab on the surface, all the drawings and information regarding the electric car burned down.

Then Henry Ford was equipped with internal combustion engines in 1914 conveyor of car production at the automaker factory launched the system and produced the famous gasoline engine "Model T" started. Low cost, high power and speed compared to electric cars equipped with an internal combustion engine the production of electric cars has been improved.

Throughout the 20th century, various companies developed electric cars from time to time they tried to lay out the release, but were not successful. Few automotive professionals have represented the 21st century in the electric car industry the wake is called the age of awakening. The cost of burning, global warming and catastrophic pollution, limited fuel reserves, hususan has been identified in the world gas reservig hajmi 179.4 trln m3 making up the annual supply volume the average gas reserve at the time of transfer is 56 years, the volume of oil reserves is 240 billion as a consequence of the prediction that the average reserve of tons will reach 52 years automobile manufacturers use electric cars that are environmentally friendly and safe improvement aroused serious interest in the idea.

Then Wang Chuanfu is the same as batteries in the development of cars went from way: he studied models from other companies and made his own versions created. There is a legend in the company that one day Chuanfu drove a new Mercedes-Benz S Class car to the factory gate and said to the workers, "him disassemble to screw, determine the structure of the parts and how it works" he says. Thus, the symbol of "reverse engineering" in China for the whole world a new car factory has appeared.

BYD F3 sedan to Toyota Corolla, S7 crossover "Lexus RX", F0 city minicar is seen from "Toyota Aygo" and S8 the convertible was similar to the Mercedes. In 2022, the ranking of leading suppliers was estimated at in the second quarter. Tesla,

which supplied 1.3 million cars, is located. As of the end of 2022, the snake Mask sales were more than 31 percent per year, with a global share of approximately 12 percentage. From the top three Volkswagen with 4%, the fourth is another Chinese producer-Wuling won a spot with 4%. According to IEA (International Energy Agency) estimates, February 2022 according to the state, there are about 16 million electric cars in the world, all this 8.57% of vehicles. In general, all electricity vehicles consume about 30 TVt / H of electricity in a year makes

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